

New Conceptions on the Equilibrium Properties of Electrolyte Solutions*

C. V. SURYANARAYANA

Central Electrochemical Research Institute, Karaikudi, Tamil Nadu-623 006

The main flaw in Debye-Hückel theory of strong electrolyte solutions, which renders it untenable is pointed out. The concept of activity in liquid solutions is shown to be erroneous due to the supervening influence of cohesion. Internal pressure, being a measure of cohesive force in a solution, is suggested as a rational basis to understand the thermodynamics of electrolyte solutions.

A new model based on the postulation of statistically oriented solvent atmospheres around ions whose radii at a given temperature decrease with increasing concentration to reach a minimum at saturation has been proposed. These atmospheres act as mere dipoles due to fluctuations in their symmetry in addition to differences in the directions of orientation of water molecules around the cations and anions. Thus viewed, experimental studies of the internal pressure of an electrolyte solution at different concentrations gives a correlation with their physico-chemical behaviour.

THE problem of calculating the effect of electrostatic ionic interactions on the equilibrium properties of strong electrolyte solutions was solved explicitly by Debye and Hückel¹. Soon after its formulation, serious objections based on statistical mechanical arguments were raised by Fowler². The validity of these objections was upheld by Frank and Thompson³.

Defects of the Debye-Hückel theory: The main defects pointed out by the previous workers may be summarized as following:

1. The basic equation of Debye-Hückel theory was obtained by combining the Maxwell-Boltzmann equation with the Poisson equation. This was considered unjustifiable as the potential of the Maxwell-Boltzmann equation is the potential of the average force whereas the potential of the Poisson equation is the average electrostatic potential^{1,2}.
2. The distribution function for ions in solution, used by Debye and Hückel, was criticised by Bagchi⁴ who proposed other distribution functions.
3. According to the Debye-Hückel theory, the activity coefficient should continue to decrease with increasing concentration. Experimental data for most salts show an initial decrease followed by a rise to high values⁵. This increase cannot be attributed to interionic attraction, but must be due to repulsion. Obviously any model which assumes only coulombic interactions cannot yield equations which will include the effects due to non-coulombic forces. In other words we cannot put into a model only coulombic forces and hope to derive equations which will cover non-coulombic effects as well.

The need, therefore, is for a theory which will formally recognise and accommodate non-coulombic forces. Devanathan⁶ proposed a cell lattice model

which fairly covered up the defects in Debye-Hückel theory but still has not stood the test of acceptability.

The main flaw in Debye-Hückel theory: The first postulate of the Debye-Hückel theory is that if the ions of an electrolyte lost their charges and became neutral particles, the solution would behave like a dilute solution obeying Henry's law. Ideal solutions are rare even in the field of non-aqueous, non-electrolyte solutions. An often quoted example is the system: ethylene bromide-propylene bromide⁷. But aqueous solutions of non-electrolytes can exhibit wide departures from ideality; for example, the osmotic coefficient of an aqueous solution of sucrose is 1.508 at 6 m. This has been explained^{8,9} by extensive hydration of the sucrose molecule; the assumption that on the average each sucrose molecule removes 4.6 water molecules from the region of "free solvent" is sufficient to account for the osmotic coefficient upto at least 2 m. It has been shown¹⁰ that the osmotic coefficient can be accounted for even upto saturation by assuming that there are eleven sites on the sucrose molecule each of which may be occupied by one water molecule. The osmotic coefficient of glycerol solutions can likewise be accounted for by postulating three hydration sites. This behaviour of non-electrolyte solutions is stressed because whatever their origin, the same effects should operate in electrolyte solutions, although modified by the charges on the ions.

In fact the total free energy of a solution can be written as,

$$G = G^{id} + G^{int} + G^{osm} + G^E$$

where G^{id} is the free energy of the ideal solution, G^{int} is the free energy resulting from interionic

*This paper is gratefully dedicated to my Guru, Professor N. R. Dhar, on the occasion of his 90th birthday.

forces of the Debye-Hückel type, G^{solv} is the free energy due to ion-solvent interaction and G^E is that due to ion-ion interactions apart from those of the Debye-Hückel type. If we go to solutions containing more than one electrolyte, their behaviour becomes complicated and interpretation more difficult.

In this background, if we can think of a measurable property of an electrolyte solution which can give a combined quantitative measure of the coulombic as well as the non-coulombic forces in terms of the properties of the constituent ions and the properties of the solvent molecules, the approach becomes more realistic.

When the solute is a gas and Henry's law is obeyed, the chemical potential of the solute in solution is given by the equation :

$$\mu_i = \mu_i^g + RT \ln C_i$$

where C_i is the concentration, in gram-moles per litre of solution and μ_i^g is the chemical potential of one mole of the solute in a solution of unit concentration.

We know that Henry's law¹¹ is inapplicable to solutions of non-electrolytes and electrolytes, more so at higher concentrations. It is also apparent that RT in the above equation has its origin in ideal gases. The non-ideality of real gases is due to the intermolecular forces of attraction. What distinguishes a liquid from a gas is the enormous cohesion in the former which can be measured by

the internal pressure, $\left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial V}\right)_T$, where U is the internal

energy and V the volume of the system. If we have a relation between the forces of cohesion, namely, the internal pressure of a liquid system and the vapour pressure above it, we have a good start.

A new approach : In this background the very idea of the chemical potential of a solute in a liquid solution being directly made proportional to $RT \ln a$ is ill-founded. Further, in an electrolyte solution to relate the activity co-efficient solely to the interionic forces is erroneous. The activity coefficient, if at all, should reflect simply the degree of cohesion in a solution system rather qualitatively.

Recently Srinivasan, Savariraj and Suryanarayana¹³ derived from statistical thermodynamical considerations, the relation between the vapour pressure P and internal pressure π_i .

$$P = P_c \exp. [-\pi V/2 RT]$$

where P_c is the critical pressure, R the gas constant and T the absolute temperature. This has been tested for 30 polar and non-polar liquids. Suryanarayana¹³ applied the above equation to electrolyte solutions and brought out the fundamental importance of internal pressure in relation to Raoult's law, osmotic pressure, osmotic and activity coefficients of electrolyte solutions.

Dack¹⁴ and Suryanarayana¹⁵ have analysed the significance and usefulness of internal pressure in liquid systems. The first review on this subject was

by Richards¹⁶. Later Hildebrand and Scott¹⁷ and Haward and Parker¹⁸ discussed the importance of internal pressure in liquids.

Suryanarayana¹⁹ recently emphasised that whatever may be the liquid system, a solvent, a mixture of solvents or a solution either of a non-electrolyte or an electrolyte, its state is thermodynamically defined by the internal pressure, the free volume and temperature.

Internal pressure reflects the sum-total of solvent-solute, solute-solute and solvent-solvent interactions in a liquid solution system. However, one has to evolve a credible method of quantitatively measuring internal pressure, particularly in an electrolyte system wherein we have all kinds of interactions.

Measurement of internal pressure : A general method of measuring internal pressure is based on the thermodynamic equation of state,

$$P = T \left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial T} \right)_V - \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial V} \right)_T$$

The first term on the right hand side is the product of temperature and the temperature coefficient of pressure and the second term is the internal pressure. For liquid solutions P is very negligible compared to the internal pressure. Hence the first term is almost equal to the second term. Hence one way of measuring internal pressure is to compute it via the temperature coefficient of pressure. For instance, Lee and Hyne²⁰ report internal pressure values of potassium chloride solutions at different concentrations and at increasing temperatures. In both, the trend is one of increase. Similarly for water, this method yields an increase of internal pressure with increase in temperature. This is rather anomalous as we know that with increase in temperature the surface tension of liquids decreases. Suryanarayana²¹ showed a quantitative relation between surface tension and internal pressure in liquid systems. Suryanarayana¹⁹ showed alternatively a new method of measuring internal pressure instead of via the temperature coefficient of pressure. This method involves measurements of ultrasonic velocity, viscosity and density of solutions. The anomalous results of the measurements of internal pressure by Lee and Hyne²⁰ can probably be due to the thermodynamic temperature coefficient of pressure, namely, $\left(\frac{\partial P}{\partial T}\right)_V$ or α/β_T being unconsciously based on gas thermodynamics. Measurements of $\left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial V}\right)_T$ by the method of Suryanarayana¹⁹ gives the expected trend of a fall in internal pressure with increasing temperature as it is based on the properties of condensed systems^{19,21}.

Suryanarayana and Kuppasami²² reported the internal pressure and free volume for electrolyte solutions of NaCl, KCl, NaNO₃, KNO₃, Na₂SO₄, K₂SO₄, ZnSO₄, CuSO₄, KI, Pb(NO₃)₂, tetramethyl ammonium chloride and one non-electrolyte, glucose, in a wide range of concentrations including saturation. A general quadratic relation has been

observed between the molality on the one hand and the internal pressure and the free volume on the other hand :

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_i &= \pi_o + Am^2 + Bm \\ V_f &= V_{f0} + Cm^3 + Dm\end{aligned}$$

π_i and V_f are for the solutions and π_o and V_{f0} are for the solvent. A, B, C and D are dependent on temperature. For all the solutions, at every concentration, the variation of either the internal pressure or the free volume with temperature can be expressed as,

$$\begin{aligned}\pi_i(T) &= a \cdot \exp. (-bT) \\ V_f(T) &= c \cdot \exp. (gT)\end{aligned}$$

where a, b, c and g are constants depending on concentration of the electrolyte and are yet to be rationalised. Glucose solutions and also pure water show the above quantitative relations.

By far the best treatment which emphasises the solvation of the ions in discussing the activity coefficients is that of Robinson and Stokes²³. But even their equation gives agreement with experimental results only upto about 2m solutions, above which it fails. We²⁴ have found that the following equation expresses quantitatively the relation between the activity coefficient and internal pressure of the medium applicable to NaCl, KCl, NH_4NO_3 solutions

$$\gamma = a \left(\frac{\pi_i}{\pi_o} \right) + b \left(\frac{\pi_i}{\pi_o} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + C$$

where a, b and c are empirical constants to be rationalised by further studies. The calculated and experimental values agree remarkably upto the highest concentration. This definitely means that activity coefficients have their origin in the differences in the degree of cohesion of different electrolyte solutions at different concentrations. Thus the behaviour of solutions in general is conditioned by their internal pressures and free volumes at a given temperature. In the case of electrolyte solutions, as with non-electrolyte solutions, the non-coulombic forces in terms of cohesive forces play a far greater role. Ion-dipole and dipole-dipole interactions assume a major role. Of these contributions, those arising from the interactions of the ion-solvent complexes are of greater significance.

A new model : When an electrolyte is dissolved in water, the important event that occurs is hydration. Friedman and Krishnan²⁴ gave a comprehensive review of the thermodynamics of ionic hydration. Frank and Wen-Yang Wen²⁵, Samoilov²⁶ and Gurney²⁷ made significant contributions to a rigorous understanding of what happens to water molecules around an ion. These advances point to the existence of primary hydration sheath in which region the solvent molecules are immobilized due to intense electrostriction. Surrounding this envelope is the region of structure breaking, and beyond this is the region of structurally normal solvent. The intermediate region is referred to as the secondary hydration sheath. The secondary

water envelope can exchange water molecules rapidly with structurally normal water, the frequency being of the order of 10^9 . Samoilov²⁶ showed that the value of the energy of activation for this exchange is very much less than the hydration energy.

Coming on to the new model, ions — both positive and negative — have radially orienting electric fields. In this orienting field, the solvent molecules get appropriately aligned²⁸ parallel to the electrostatic field generated by the positive or negative ions resulting in a minimum potential energy. Beyond the primary hydration limit also, one may have to think in terms of an atmosphere of solvent molecules around the ions having statistically a spherical symmetry. We may call this statistically oriented solvent atmosphere. The radius of this atmosphere should be a function of temperature, concentration of the electrolyte and specifically the surface density of the charge on the ions — positive or negative. Thus the statistically oriented solvent atmosphere either for a cation or for an anion should effectively behave with interactions as between dipoles. It must be clear that any disturbance in the thermodynamic equilibrium state of the system should perturb these atmospheres and disturb the overall entropy of the system. Once this picture is accepted, then follows the same usual way of looking at an electrolyte solution as we do at a pure liquid or a non-electrolyte solution. In other words, as Pitzer²⁹ rightly pointed out, a really satisfactory general theory of non-electrolytes could be transferred to the concentrated electrolyte problem.

The radius of the statistically oriented solvent atmosphere naturally goes on diminishing as the concentration tends to increase towards saturation. One should imagine that at saturation concentration a minimum radius of the statistically oriented solvent atmosphere is obtained. What requires to be looked at in this model is the balance between attractive and repulsive forces in the solutions due to statistically oriented solvent atmospheres. By very definition and its nature, internal pressure of a solution is a balance between the attractive and repulsive forces. However, in the equations given by Suryanarayana and Kuppasami²² relating to internal pressure of a solution either to the concentration or to the activity coefficient, the constants involved in the quadratic equations are such that the one belonging to the higher power term relates to attractive forces and the other relating to the lower power term to the repulsive forces. In other words, a rationalised theory of solutions which can be common both for non-electrolyte and electrolyte solutions consists in working out attractive and repulsive forces quantitatively based on the overall internal pressure of a solution. This model makes the ions, taken together with the statistically oriented solvent atmospheres, similar to floating dipoles contributing to the overall cohesion of the solution. They may be taken as dipoles because the spherical symmetry should be expected to be perturbed due

to random fluctuations. The solvent atmosphere, if spherically symmetrical, should mean neutral spheres in the case of both cationic and anionic atmospheres. For cohesion to exist, dispersion forces are a minimum necessity. Hence in a fluctuating situation, the spherical symmetry is perturbed statistically and gives rise to dispersion forces. Even otherwise, due to the differences in the directions of orientation of solvent molecules around the cations and anions taken together with the fluctuations in the symmetry of the oriented solvent atmospheres, dipolar type of interactions should be expected between the floating oriented atmospheres.

It is often said that Passinsky's method³⁰ yields ionic hydration values which are too high at lower concentrations and fall off reaching a limit as one approaches saturation. This is an indirect evidence of the existence of statistically oriented solvent atmospheres around an ion neutralising the central ionic charge.

In this background one should imagine that at saturation concentration not only the radius of the statistically oriented solvent atmospheres should be the minimum but also the potential energy due to this arrangement should be the minimum compared to other lower concentrations. One can not think of free solvent molecules not forming a part of these spheres of atmospheres. Bencowitz³¹ found empirically that by using the ratio of any molality of an electrolyte solution to that at saturation, which he called the "degree of saturation", instead of the molal concentration, vapour pressure lowerings even at high concentrations were explained by simpler relationships. Suryanarayana and Venkatesan found similar relationships³²⁻³⁴ with viscosity and conductance in electrolyte solutions. Suryanarayana³⁵ made an analysis of these ideas connected with saturation concentration and suggested the term concentration potential for the degree of saturation. From Suryanarayana's³⁵ analysis, it looks that the concentration dependent physical properties of electrolyte solutions are quantitatively related to the size of these statistically oriented solvent atmospheres. Further, the variation in any physical property with concentration is expressed in a simpler quantitative way when the ratio between the size of the solvent atmosphere at a given concentration to that at saturation is considered. The size of the solvent atmosphere seems to be conditioned by the overall attractive and repulsive forces as a result of the sum-total of 1-2, 2-2 and 1-1 interactions. At a given concentration the sizes of the cationic and anionic solvent atmospheres need not be the same. But their variation with concentration follows simpler laws when one takes their ratio with those at saturation. Internal pressure being a measurable property should be able to explain the behaviour of mixed electrolyte solutions also.

A further evidence of the role of statistically oriented solvent atmospheres is that at a given concentration of an electrolyte solution even upto saturation concentration, Suryanarayana and Kuppasami³² reported that the variation of equivalent conductance with temperature is such that,

$$\Lambda_e(T) = h - g \cdot \pi_i(T)$$

where equivalent conductance virtually varies with internal pressure at the respective temperature, h and g being constants. One should expect that an increase in temperature will have a disorienting influence on the solvent atmosphere due to thermal fluctuations introducing more randomness and lowering the internal pressure particularly due to the inter-solvent atmosphere forces becoming lesser.

Acknowledgement

The author expresses his thanks to Dr. H.V.K. Udupa, Director, Central Electrochemical Research Institute, Karaikudi for permission to communicate this paper.

References

1. P. DEBYE and E. HÜCKEL, *Physikal. Z.*, 1923, 24, 185.
2. R. H. FOWLER, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 23, 434.
3. H. S. FRANK and P. T. THOMSON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1959, 31, 1086.
4. S. N. BAGCHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 29, 199.
5. E. A. GUGGENHEIM and R. H. STOKES, "Equilibrium Properties of Aqueous Solutions of Single Strong Electrolytes", Pergamon Press, 1969, p. 141.
6. M. A. V. DEVANATHAN, *J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 256.
7. J. VON ZAWIDSKI, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1900, 35, 129.
8. G. SCATCHARD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 43, 2406.
9. R. A. ROBINSON and R. H. STOKES, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, 65, 1954.
10. R. H. STOKES and R. A. ROBINSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1966, 70, 2126.
11. W. HENRY, *Phil. Trans.*, 1903, 29, 274.
12. G. M. SRINIVASAN, G. A. SAVARIRAJ and C. V. SURYANARAYANA, *Indian J. Phys.*, 1978, 52A, 23.
13. C. V. SURYANARAYANA, *J. Acoust. Soc. India*, 1978, 6, 25.
14. M. R. J. DACK, *Chem. Soc. Rev. (London)*, 1975, 4, 211.
15. C. V. SURYANARAYANA, *J. Acoust. Soc. India*, 1977, 5, 111.
16. T. W. RICHARDS, *Chem. Rev.*, 1925, 2, 315.
17. J. H. HILDEBRAND and R. L. SCOTT, "The Solubility of Non-electrolytes", 3rd Edn., Reinhold, New York, 1950.
18. R. N. HAWARD and B. M. PARKER, *J. Phys. Chem. Ithaca*, 1968, 72, 1842.
19. C. V. SURYANARAYANA, *J. Acoust. Soc. India*, 1979, 7, 131.
20. I. LEE and J. B. HYNNE, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1973, 51, 1885.
21. C. V. SURYANARAYANA, *J. Acoust. Soc. India*, 1979, 7, 107.
22. C. V. SURYANARAYANA and J. KUPPUSAMI, *J. Acoust. Soc. India*, (under publication).
23. J. ROBBINS, "Ions in Solution (2)—An Introduction to Electrochemistry", Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1972.
24. H. L. FRIEDMAN and C. V. KRISHNAN, "Thermodynamics of ionic hydration", Chap. I in Vol. 3; "Aqueous Solutions of Simple Electrolytes in Water", (Ed.) Felix Franks, Plenum Press, 1973.

25. H. S. FRANK and WEN-YANG WEN, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 24, 133.
26. O. Y. SAMOILOV, *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, 24, 141.
27. R. W. GURNEY, "Ionic Processes in Solution", McGraw-Hill Book Co., Inc., New York, 1953.
28. M. A. V. DEVANATHAN, *J. Sci. Industr. Res.*, 1961, 20B, 275.
29. K. S. PITZER, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1973, 2, 186.
30. A. PASSYNSKY, *Acta Physiochem.*, 1938, 8, 385.
31. I. BENCOWATZ, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 1432.
32. C. V. SURYANARAYANA and V. K. VENKATESAN, *Nature*, 1956, 178, 1461.
33. C. V. SURYANARAYANA and V. K. VENKATESAN, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, 54, 1709.
34. C. V. SURYANARAYANA and V. K. VENKATESAN, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1958, 16, 149; 1958, 16, 339 and 1959, 19, 441.
35. C. V. SURYANARAYANA, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. India*, 1973, 43(A), 6.